

$$Y = 21.84 + 0.385 N - 0.006333 N^2$$

Analysis of this response equation revealed that sugar beet tops (depending upon the rate of inorganic N used) were

equivalent to 32-40 kg of urea N, or an average of 37 kg N/ha. The percent utilization of the applied N through tops also varied with urea N rates, with an overall average of 26% (Table 2).

Results suggest that sugar beet tops should be incorporated into the soil rather than be removed from a field before rice is planted. ■

Top pruning of *Sesbania rostrata* to increase rice grain yield

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Seed availability is a major constraint in the use of *S. rostrata* as a green manure (GM) crop for rice. Pruning the top of sesbania at the juvenile stage can promote production of axillary buds and new branches, thus resulting in higher biomass production and higher N accumulation. We studied whether pruning can increase biomass production of pre-ripened sesbania to compensate for a lower seeding rate.

Sesbania seeds were sown at increasing rates (see table) in rows 40 cm apart in well-tilled 3- × 6-m plots. The

experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Two treatments of *A. afraspera* were compared with sesbania. Two fallow weed-free treatments were maintained as controls. The GM crop was irrigated and received no fertilizer.

The top 1/3 of the treated plants were pruned at 25 d after emergence (DE). The pruned tops were weighed, and then returned to the plots. The plants were cut at ground level at 55 DE and soil-incorporated after recording height and fresh weight. All plots received 13 kg P/ha and 25 kg K/ha during soil puddling.

IR72 rice was transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing. In one control treatment, 65 kg N/ha was applied basally and

35 kg N/ha was applied at 4 d before panicle initiation. The other control plot received no N. Plots were kept flooded until harvest.

Pruning the tops of the GM plants did not improve their biomass production. The unpruned plants were significantly taller at 55 DE and generally had greater total dry matter than the pruned plants. Plant height and dry matter increased with increasing seeding rate, particularly in the unpruned treatments.

Compared with the zero N control, the application of N and GM significantly increased rice plant height, grain yield, and total dry matter yields (TDMY), but not tiller number. The N-fertilized and green-manured rice yields were comparable. Pruning the GM plants generally had no effect on rice grain yield, TDMY, height, and tiller number. Regardless of the pruning treatment, increasing the seed rate from 10 to 40 kg/ha did not clearly benefit grain yield and other parameters. ■

Effect of pruning* and seeding rate of green manures *S. rostrata* and *A. afraspera* on rice performance. IRRI, 1990 wet season.

Treatment no.	Sesbania management		Sesbania		Rice (IR72)				
	Seed rate (kg/ha)	Pruning management	Dry matter (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	TDMY (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers (no./m ²)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)
1	10	Pruned (P)	0.48	77	2.7	7.3	83	329	300
2	10	Unpruned (UP)	0.38	90	2.7	7.2	83	343	314
3	20	P	0.37	71	2.5	7.9	84	337	309
4	20	UP	1.41	111	2.9	8.6	86	341	310
5	30	P	1.03	89	2.8	7.8	83	319	293
6	30	UP	1.82	123	2.6	7.8	87	366	326
7	40	P	0.88	87	2.8	8.2	85	329	302
8	40	UP	2.04	130	2.6	8.3	85	360	325
9	Fallow	(0 N on rice)	-	-	2.3	5.9	79	310	279
10	Fallow	(100 kg N/ha on rice)	-	-	2.6	6.3	81	306	274
11	20	<i>A. afraspera</i> (P)	0.84	60	2.7	7.8	86	345	319
12	20	<i>A. afraspera</i> (UP)	1.45	87	2.6	8.3	85	339	311
		CV (%)	51.9	11.5	7.2	10.4	2.7	12.7	13.0
		Comparison ^b							
		T1 × T2	ns	*	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T3 × T4	**	**	**	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T5 × T6	*	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T7 × T8	**	**	ns	ns	*	ns	ns
		T1, 2 × T3, 4	**	ns	ns	*	ns	ns	ns
		T9 × T10	?	?	*	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T11 × T12	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T11, 12 × T3, 4	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T9 × T1, 2	ns	**	**	**	**	ns	ns
		T10 × T1, 2	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^aThe top 1/3 of the GM was pruned at 25 DE. ^b*, ** = significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively. ns = nonsignificant.

Fertilizer management

Response of Mukthi (CTH1) ratoon to nutrition in coastal Karnataka, India

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Rice predominates over other crops in coastal Karnataka during the three growing seasons. We studied the possibilities of rice ratooning during 1989-90 rabi season (Sep-Dec). Mukthi was found to be a good ratooner among the five varieties tested. To improve the performance of the ratoon crop, nutritional parameters were imposed on Mukthi ratoon at the Regional Research Station (RRS), Brahmavar, during 1991 rabi. Soils are lateritic, rich in organic C,

low in available P and K, and have a pH of 5.1 (air-dried soil).

We applied different amounts of N with farmyard manure (FYM) and Agroplus (a liquid micronutrient fertilizer) on a Mukthi ratoon crop. The experiment was laid out in a strip-plot design, replicated three times.

Effect of nutrition on Mukthi (CTH1) ratoon rice. RRS, Brahmavar, India, 1991 rabi.

Treatment ^a	Tillers/hill (no.) at 21 DAR ^b	Grains/panicle (no.)	Grain wt/panicle (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
F ₁ 0	7.0	46.1	0.67	1.6
F ₁ AP	6.4	48.6	0.73	1.7
F ₁ FYM	7.2	50.6	0.75	1.9
F ₂ 0	11.0	57.4	0.88	2.3
F ₂ AP	11.6	59.4	0.93	2.5
F ₂ FYM	12.2	56.7	0.87	2.3
F ₃ 0	14.4	61.2	0.95	2.7
F ₃ AP	15.2	65.2	1.04	3.0
F ₃ FYM	15.6	62.1	0.98	2.8
F ₄ 0	13.4	56.5	0.88	2.7
F ₄ AP	14.2	56.2	0.89	2.8
F ₄ FYM	14.0	55.4	0.87	2.7

For fertilizer levels

S.Em ±	0.2	0.7	0.02	0.1
LSD (0.05)	0.8	2.3	0.07	0.2
CV (%)	6.0	4.0	7.00	9.0

For AP and FYM

S.Em ±	0.1	0.9	0.01	0.02
LSD (0.05)	0.2	ns	ns	0.1
CV (%)	1.0	5.0	5.0	2.0

For interaction

For comparing two nutrition means at the same level of fertilizer	-	-	-	-
S.Em ±	-	-	-	0.1
LSD (0.05)	-	-	-	0.3

For comparing two fertilizer means at the same level of nutrition

S.Em ±	-	-	-	0.1
LSD (0.05)	-	-	-	0.2
CV (%)	6.0	4.0	5.0	5.0

^aF₁ = 0-25-25 kg NPK/ha, F₂ = 25-25-25 kg NPK/ha, F₃ = 50-25-25 kg NPK/ha, F₄ = 75-25-25 kg NPK/ha, AP = Agroplus 2 ml/liter at 15 DAR, FYM = 2.5 t/ha on ratooning day, 0 = control ^bDays after ratooning.

Results showed that fertilizer levels up to 50 kg N/ha increased grain yield (see table). FYM and Agroplus had a marginal effect on the crop at all N levels. Tillers per hill, grain number, and weight per panicle showed a trend similar to that of grain yield. The ratoon crop matured in

70 d; the preceding main crop took 102 d and yielded 3.9 t grain/ha.

Mukthi can be ratoon-cropped successfully by applying 50 kg N/ha; it can be harvested about a month earlier than the main crop. ■

Influence of green manures on P use efficiency in rice

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We studied the effect of green manure crops cowpea *Vigna unguiculata*, dhaincha *Sesbania aculeata*, and sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea* on P use efficiency in rice cultivar PR106 compared with a fallow field over 2 yr. We incorporated 60-d-old unfertilized green manure into soil 1 d before

transplanting rice. Rice received 0, 13, or 26 kg P/ha as single superphosphate along with a basal dose of 120 kg N/ha as urea and 50 kg K/ha as muriate of potash. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Results were based on total dry matter accumulation and total P uptake by green manures. Sunn hemp produced the most dry matter and contained relatively higher amounts of P (see table).

Rice grain yield was significantly higher in cowpea-manured plots and lowest in fallow plots (see figure). The rice crop responded significantly to 13 kg P/ha in green-manured plots and to 26 kg P/ha in fallow plots, showing the beneficial effects of green manures as substitutes for fertilizer P in rice (see figure).

Cowpea-manured plots produced the highest yield at 6 t grain/ha with 13 kg P/ha, perhaps because cowpea decomposes

Effect of green manure and applied P on rice grain yield (av of 2 yr). Ludhiana, India.

Dry matter accumulation, total P uptake by various green manure crops, and fertilizer P use efficiency of rice as affected by various green manures. Ludhiana, India.

Green manure crop	Dry matter produced (t/ha)		Total P uptake (kg/ha)		Fertilizer P use efficiency of rice ^a (kg grain/kg applied P)	
	1st yr	2d yr	1st	2d yr	13 kg applied P/ha	25 kg applied P/ha
Cowpea	4.25	3.92	12.3	11.1	108 (41)	41 (21)
Dhaincha	3.99	3.04	11.4	8.7	85 (18)	54 (34)
Sunn hemp	5.00	4.52	12.2	11.2	89 (22)	49 (29)
Fallow	-	-	-	-	67	20
LSD (0.05)	0.57	0.59	ns	2.6		

^aAv of 2 yr. Values in parentheses show increase in P use efficiency over fallow plots.